

THEORETICAL AND LEGAL BASIS OF INCREASING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY IN COTTON GROWING

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Abstract. The article analyzes the issues of increasing the economic efficiency of the cotton industry, fulfilling the requirements of the country's food strategy directions, and ensuring food safety.

Key words: economic efficiency, profitability, key indicators, profit, material cost, income.

INTRODUCTION. Increasing the economic efficiency of the cotton sector serves, first of all, to fulfill the requirements of the country's food strategy and ensure food security. On the other hand, this goal is achieved through rational use of the existing labor, land, water, material and financial resources of enterprises included in the cotton sector, regardless of their forms of ownership, based on improving economic relations between them. In short, increasing the efficiency of production in the sector largely depends on the rational use of existing resources. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 6, 2020 "On measures for the widespread introduction of market principles in the cotton sector", the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 27, 2020 "On measures to improve the system of testing and certification of agricultural and land reclamation techniques", and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5853 dated October 23, 2019 "On approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" set the task of ensuring the implementation of the Resolution, including the introduction of market principles that ensure free competition in agriculture, the abolition of state orders in the cultivation of cotton and grain, increasing the economic efficiency of production and the interests of producers, and creating additional jobs through the widespread attraction of investments.

One of the main directions of effective development of the cotton sector in Uzbekistan is the full implementation of the legal framework for the reform of agrarian and economic relations in rural areas. Over the years of independence, more than 180 regulatory legal acts have been adopted in the agricultural sector of the country to increase their effectiveness. Also, about 500 regulatory legal acts related to the agricultural sector with certain features are in force. One of the main requirements of the current era is not only the production of raw materials in agriculture, including cotton growing, but also the correct and effective implementation of its processing and sale. Because the main part of the added value created, that is, income, is formed precisely in the following areas. Previously, in our republic, the issues of full use of the factors of increasing the efficiency of the main products of cotton growing have been resolved separately for raw cotton, cotton fiber, cotton oil, cottonseed and other cotton products.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. A number of leading agrarian economists and theorists of our republic, including: A.A. Abdug'aniev, A.A. Shokirov, A. Juraev, A.Z. Zokirov, A.S.

Samutali, D.Q. Ahmedov, N.S. Khushmatov, R.V. Abdullaev, R.Kh. Khusanov, F.Q. Qayumov, F.Kh. Nazarova, Ch.M. Murodov, E.J. Yusupov, O'.P. Umurzakov, Q.A. Khasanjanov, Q.A. Choriev and others, conducted scientific research on the issues of developing the cotton growing complex and increasing its economic efficiency in our country during the years of independence. N.S. Khushmatov, R.V. Abdullaev and E.J. It is worth noting that as a result of scientific research conducted by the Yusupovs, a number of scientifically based proposals were developed on increasing the efficiency of cotton fiber production and sales, forming inter-sectoral balance in reforming the cotton growing complex, and the economic feasibility of distributing cotton varieties by region.

RESULTS. The cotton complex plays an important role in the socio-economic development process and is of great importance for the country's economy, which is dominated by its successful development. Cotton products processed in factories are a very important raw material for the light and food industries. Products obtained from cotton are also used in heavy industry. Up to 300 types of consumer and technical products are made from cotton raw materials. The importance of cotton growing and cotton ginning industries in the economy of our country is significant. The more the industry develops, the more other sectors of the national economy develop. From this point of view, the further development of cotton growing is one of the priority areas of our republic. As is known, our country has long been famous for its climate, fertile soil, underground and surface resources. Currently, 3.0-3.2 million tons of raw cotton are produced in our country annually. The main factor in achieving such success is the constant attention paid to the sector by our government, and in particular, the introduction of economic incentives, scientific and technical achievements, and advanced technologies, which have paved the way for the farming movement. Thanks to the gradual reforms, the material and technical base of farms is being strengthened year by year.

It is known that our republic ranks sixth in terms of cotton acreage among more than 80 major cotton-growing countries in the world, providing an average of 3-4 percent of the world's cotton production.

However, the average cotton yield per hectare in the republic is 30-35 t/ha, which is significantly lower than the indicators of foreign countries in this regard. For example, in Turkey, the yield is 70 t/ha. Therefore, eliminating some of the negative results observed in the cotton sub-complex, bringing the efficiency of this sector to the level of advanced countries, and finding solutions to the problems of increasing cotton yield and soil fertility are necessary conditions for ensuring the competitiveness of the sector in the domestic and international markets.

It is known that fertile land and water resources are limited. Increasing the efficiency of using existing resources? First of all, this is achieved by increasing the yield from each hectare of cotton. Increasing productivity is associated with the implementation of high-quality and short-term agro-technological processes, as well as the application of innovative and digital technologies to the industry.

One of the main directions of effective development of the cotton sector in Uzbekistan is the full implementation of the legal framework for reforming agrarian and economic relations in rural areas. Over the years of independence, more than 180 regulatory legal acts have been adopted in the agricultural sector of the country to improve the effectiveness of the measures taken in our country and their implementation. In addition, about 500 regulatory legal acts related to the agricultural sector with certain features are in force.

In particular, in order to further develop the agricultural and cotton sector of our country, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 6, 2020 "On measures for the widespread introduction of market principles in the cotton sector", the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 22, 2020 "On measures for the further development of cotton and textile production", the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 27, 2020 "On measures to improve the system of testing and certification of agricultural and land reclamation techniques", the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 No. PF-5853 "On approval of the Strategy for the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030", the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 25, 2022 "On measures to improve soil fertility and "On measures to increase productivity and support the introduction of new irrigation technologies" were adopted. In order to ensure the implementation of these decisions, very wide-ranging and serious reforms are being carried out in the agriculture of our country. In particular, state orders for cotton and grain have been abandoned and pricing has been liberalized. A cluster system has been introduced in product production and all conditions have been created for their development. The goal is to sharply increase the volume of products, create high added value and new jobs, and most importantly, increase income and profitability. **CONCLUSION.** In conclusion, it can be noted that in modern economic conditions, the development of the cotton complex, which is of decisive importance for the country's economy, gives a powerful impetus to the development of raw material production and industrial sectors. This is also clearly seen in the experience of developed countries. From this point of view, stimulating the development of the cotton complex and increasing its competitiveness is of great importance for the national economic interests of our country. Promoting the development of the cotton complex can become the basis for the development of other structural complexes of the national economy.

Increasing economic efficiency in cotton growing is associated with the following factors:

- the need for fertile, flat lands for cotton cultivation and the need to strictly adhere to the agrotechnology of cotton cultivation, feeding, irrigation and processing;
- eliminating seasonality in the organization of labor and providing labor resources with uniform and full-time work throughout the year;
- changes in demand for cotton fiber in the world market, the need to harvest cotton in a short time, etc.
- determining the necessary ratio of organic and mineral fertilizers when carrying out agrotechnical measures, ensuring that crops are irrigated in accordance with established standards on time, and placing high-yielding, promising cotton varieties resistant to various diseases in the regions;

As a result of research, indicators expressing the efficiency of cotton cultivation were systematized. These indicators, covering relevant general economic indicators, allow assessing the efficiency of using all types of resources in the sector. When calculating the economic efficiency of production achieved by the farm as a result of the measures taken, it should be expressed in the form of natural, value, relative and qualitative indicators.

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